

NATURANCE

Innovation Lab Guidebook

Grantham Research Institute for Climate Change
and the Environment
London School of Economics and Political Science

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Document History

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Table of Contents

Document History.....	2
1. Introduction – What are Innovation Labs?	4
2. Preparing for an Innovation Lab (Pre-lab Phase)	6
2.1 Suggesting and selecting themes.....	6
2.2 Deciding on NATURANCE consortium member to lead the Innovation Lab	7
2.3 Selecting participants for the Innovation Lab.....	7
3. Planning the Innovation Lab (Pre-lab Phase)	9
3.1 Format and time frame.....	9
3.2 Logistics and Tools.....	9
3.3 Setting expectations	10
4. Running an Innovation Lab	11
4.1 Workshops/Meetings	11
4.2 Preparing and running the first meeting or workshop of the innovation lab	11
4.3 Canvassing innovative solutions	12
4.4 Discuss, test and finalise solution.....	12
5. Building a Business Case	14
5.1 Case Study: WBCSD Blueprint	14
6. Reporting and disseminating the Innovation Lab outcomes (Post-lab Phase).....	16
6.1 Quantitative assessment of Innovation Lab outcomes using scorecard summary	16
6.2 Qualitative assessment of Innovation Lab	17
6.3 Innovation Lab report structure	18
6.4 Innovation Lab review and submission process	20
References	21
Appendix.....	22
A. Scorecard.....	22
B. Innovation Lab Canvas	23

1. Introduction – What are Innovation Labs?

Innovation labs (IL) are safe spaces that offer a collaborative environment where different agents are joined together for the purpose of innovating and generating new solutions (Arrighi et al. 2016). The NATURANCE ILs bring together many different types of actors and knowledge, fostering experimentation and experiential social learning (Koelle et al. 2019). The format gives participants the freedom to challenge dominant or business-as-usual approaches, and to innovate new pathways for societal transformation.

Key to their success is how the labs are facilitated and how different voices can be heard (Koelle et al. 2019, Reed & Abernethy 2018). In line with commonly agreed practices for ILs the management structure of the NATURANCE hubs follow the principles of good governance, reflecting the diversity in the composition of the partners and ensuring an open and high-quality decision-making process. This document provides guidance on how to plan and run a NATURANCE IL and how to report its outcomes.¹

The structure of this document follows the three stages of an IL:

- pre-lab phase – preparation (Sections 2 & 3)
- innovation lab phase (Sections 4 & 5)
- post-lab phase – reporting and dissemination (Section 6)

The IL approach is based on the design thinking process, which has its roots in product development, but is increasingly used in the public sector e.g. to innovate policymaking (Mintrom & Luetjens 2016). Design thinking starts with the observation of the status quo followed by the exploration of the challenge.

During the actual IL, the problem is defined, potential solutions are canvassed and discussed with the group. The definition and exploration of the problem in combination with potential solutions or innovations are used to develop a prototype business case, which is then critically stress tested and questioned to identify potential knowledge gaps and barriers for implementation. The outcomes of this process are reported in a scorecard-type summary and disseminated to the intended audience (NATURANCE consortium members, external reviewers).

¹ This is an updated version that considers feedback and lessons learnt from Round I of the Innovation Labs

Box 1: Types of Innovations (adapted from UNICEF, 2012)

Innovation in Programmes: Using new technology and ideas to serve vulnerable regions that would benefit from NbS.

Innovation in Products: Creating processes that support the efficient and transparent creation, adaption or uptake of NbS insurance products. These process innovations have a strong equity focus, ensuring that process is driven by local needs.

Innovation in Processes: Increasing efficiencies in difficult economic environments. Improving the ability to target resources to monitor and manage results.

Innovation in Partnerships: New collaborations with donors, other insurance and finance stakeholders, national and local governments, civil society and the private sector

2. Preparing for an Innovation Lab (Pre-lab Phase)

2.1 Suggesting and selecting themes

In the first stage representatives of a knowledge network (KN) interested in participating in an IL collaboratively explore potential themes for the IL. Questions that can help find potential themes include:

- What thematic foci are relevant and for whom (stakeholders, industry and policy priorities)?
- What are the hazards, scales and geographies of particular interest (neighbourhood to transnational challenges)?
- What gaps have the KN identified in their previous work?
- What unique skills and knowledge can the KN bring to the IL?

The range of potential themes is kept deliberately broad to allow the KN representatives to shape their own IL rather than follow a prescriptive top-down approach. Experts from the NATURANCE consortium can help to steer and facilitate the process to find a theme for the IL.

The ILs should cover one or more of the three following areas:

- NbS in risk transfer
- NbS in investment
- NbS in advisory

Expected outcome: Title and an abstract or short statement which summarises the proposed IL including a description of the challenge and the intended aim of the IL (200 words max, see Box 2).

Box 2: Example template for a lab statement

We suggest focusing this lab around **[Specific subject area]** – and specifically building support for **[more specificity]** – a project that is being initiated by **[linked to for example a previous activity or identified challenge]** to **[impact goes here]**.

2.2 Deciding on NATURANCE consortium member to lead the Innovation Lab

Each IL is run under the leadership of one NATURANCE consortium member. Each consortium member is leading at least one IL over the course of the NATURANCE project. Once the KN representatives have agreed on a theme for their IL, they decide on which NATURANCE consortium member is best suited to lead their IL. Not every IL will have the same criteria to decide which consortium member is most suitable, but factors that can be considered are the additional expertise e.g. through their academic work, access to a network the IL would like to tap into, existing collaborations and/or the leadership skills of the consortium member.

Both the NATURANCE consortium members and the KN are regularly updated on the formation of ILs, so both sides can actively approach each other and find the right match between IL theme and consortium lead.

Expected outcome: Short written agreement between NATURANCE member and KN representatives about their collaboration in an IL, including the title of the IL, name of the NATURANCE consortium member and representatives of the KN.

Innovations Labs – Round I:

For Round I, three innovation lab pitches were presented during the first Naturance Webstival on June 14 -15 2023 marking the kick-off for the first round of innovation labs.

After the three pitches, three parallel virtual break-out rooms for each innovation lab were provided as a space to further discuss the idea of the innovation lab and get feedback from the Webstival participants and expert groups. Webstival participants were also able to join one of the breakout rooms to show their interest in the innovation lab, to provide feedback and explore opportunities to collaborate. All three break-out sessions had good participation rates and provided valuable feedback and networking opportunities for the innovation lab leads.

2.3 Selecting participants for the Innovation Lab

Once the KN representatives have agreed on a theme for their IL and established a working relationship with the NATURANCE consortium member leading the IL, participants for the IL can be selected. ILs are intended to have

between 5-10 participants, but the exact number can vary depending on the specific topic and need for expertise. The selection or nomination of participants should be guided by the following questions:

- What expertise do we need in our IL and what expertise can we provide?
- Which sectors and stakeholders should be represented?
- How do we involve and integrate governmental partners / policymakers' views throughout, as appropriate?

In addition to the required expertise and representation of all relevant sectors, the selection should be informed by equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) criteria including gender, race, disability, and age. During the selection process, EDI criteria should be embraced by actively encouraging underrepresented members to join the IL.

Expected outcome: List of names and contact details of each participant of the IL including a confirmation that their contact details will be used to coordinate the IL and will be deleted after the completion of the IL in accordance with GDPR principles.

3. Planning the Innovation Lab (Pre-lab Phase)

Once the IL has selected a theme, has agreed which NATURANCE consortium member will lead the lab and has selected the IL participants, the group can start planning on how to run the IL. This stage is facilitated by the London School of Economics.

3.1 Format and time frame

The IL participants need to agree on the format and time frame of the IL. ILs can last between **1 and 9 months** but should **not exceed 9 months**. Over the course of the IL a series of workshops, small group discussions or roundtable discussions are organised. In-between those meetings the participants follow up on action items they agreed on in the previous meeting. The number of meetings and preparation time between the meetings is down to the participants of the IL, but we suggest that participants only commit to an IL when they are able to join **at least three 1.5 – 3 hour meetings** with a few hours of individual preparatory work in between, which accounts for around **2 hours per meeting** (i.e. **a total of 15 hours or 2 work days**).

The meetings can stretch out over a longer time period (up to 9 months) but can also be condensed into a two-day workshop. The format of the meetings also depends on whether the meetings are online, in-person or in a hybrid format, with full day meetings being easier to facilitate in person due to stronger fatigue effects during long online meetings.

Expected outcome: Agreed time frame and format of the IL including the number of hours expected to be committed to the IL and the official start and end dates of the IL.

3.2 Logistics and Tools

When participants of the IL have agreed to a format and time frame, they need to decide on the individual meetings or workshops that should be held as part of the IL. Depending on the location of the participants, budget and willingness to travel, the IL can be organised as a series of online, in-person or hybrid events. In case of an in-person or hybrid event, a suitable venue needs to be selected and booked. ILs can also be combined or integrated into existing events such as conferences or other meetings or workshops.

The dates for all meetings or events should be set in the planning phase to avoid delays when running the IL. Planning for a 10% buffer on top of the initial time commitment allows for an agile response to unforeseen roadblocks or delays.

For online and hybrid events, participants need to agree on a suitable virtual meeting platform such as Zoom or MS Teams. To allow for virtual collaboration, visual collaboration platforms such as Miro can be used for canvassing and sharing ideas across participants. The IL canvas shown in the Appendix will be provided as an online version in Miro for ILs to use. For in-person events flipcharts or whiteboards can be used.

Expected outcomes: Agreed dates for the individual sessions of the IL.

For in-person events: Venue selected, booked/reserved and travel funds secured for all participants.

For hybrid events: confirmation that selected venue has hybrid capabilities.

For online events: Virtual meeting platform and tools for remote collaborative working agreed.

Innovation Labs Round I Format

Round I partners adopted different formats when conducting their ILs. The following table highlights that there is no set format for conducting an IL. The format is contingent on the partner leading the IL, the topic and the experts involved.

NATURANCE consortium member	Format
LSE	Virtual workshops with select key experts
IIASA	In-person/Hybrid workshops with key experts from an existing external project
IVM	Hybrid workshops with select key partners and experts

3.3 Setting expectations

While the key problems that will be addressed in the IL are defined in detail during the first session of the IL, setting the overall expectations and what outcomes to aim for, given the theme, format and time frame of the IL helps to steer the group while running the IL. This should be done by the NATURANCE consortium member while preparing to run the IL. The expectations for the IL should be informed by the following questions:

- What challenge will the IL address and what is out of scope?
- Is there any ambiguity in the concepts and terms that will be addressed in the IL, which need to be clarified with the participants in the first?
- Are there any risks that could lead to an unsuccessful outcome of the IL; how can these risks be managed?

4. Running an Innovation Lab

This section provides guidance on the individual steps for running an IL and the expected outcomes. The NATURANCE consortium member leading the IL is responsible for structuring the inputs from all IL participants.

4.1 Workshops/Meetings

We suggest a **minimum of three meetings** (1.5-3 hours each) to successfully run an IL:

- *1st meeting*: Define the challenge that will be addressed in the IL, including a short problem statement and the identified gaps.
- *2nd meeting*: Canvas potential ideas to overcome challenges and gaps with an innovative solution. Focus on implementation, financing and impact of the innovative solution.
- *3rd meeting*: Critically discuss and test the canvased innovations using the broad categories and questions outlined in the scorecard.
- *Additional meetings/workshops*: Iteratively improve canvased innovation until all participants agree that innovation has reached saturation on implementation, financing, and impact.

At the beginning of each meeting one participant will be nominated by the leading NATURANCE consortium member to take notes and record the outcomes of the meeting based on the agreed format of the meeting (e.g. Miro Board, Flip Charts).

The NATURANCE consortium member leads through the meeting, making sure all participants can make their contribution by keeping to time and by encouraging all participants to provide inputs. It is also the responsibility of the NATURANCE consortium member to ensure that participants stick to the agreed topic, while at the same time allowing for a broader discussion where necessary and relevant for providing innovative ideas. In case the NATURANCE consortium member needs additional guidance in running the IL, **the canvas template in the Appendix can help structure the IL.**

4.2 Preparing and running the first meeting or workshop of the innovation lab

The first meeting is crucial to the success of the IL as participants define the problem to be addressed in detail and define the role of each participant in the IL. The NATURANCE consortium member leading the IL may seek additional facilitating support from LSE and can ask participants to prepare and send specific information in the run-up to the first meeting/workshop to support them

in their leadership role. This can include specific skill/role profiles of each participant and/or short statements on why they think this is an important topic and their expectations from the IL.

Expected outcomes: Defined problem for which the IL will develop a solution/innovation. Roles for each participant of the IL defined and how they intend to contribute to developing the innovation.

4.3 Canvassing innovative solutions

At the second meeting, when canvassing/developing innovative solutions, the participants can use the centre part of the canvas template (see Appendix). After defining the problem in the first meeting, the problem statement is verified with all participants, which also acts as a reminder of what has been agreed in the first meeting / workshop of the IL.

Participants can then start developing solutions to the individual elements of the identified problem in a brainstorming session led by the NATURANCE consortium lead. The lead also helps to structure the inputs provided by the participants e.g. by grouping the suggestions using different coloured post-it notes.

Expected outcomes: Verified problem and prototype innovation or solution in agreement with all participants of the IL.

4.4 Discuss, test and finalise solution

The third meeting is used to test the suggested solutions or innovations with the aim to have a finalised, comprehensive solution in the shape of a business case in response to the initially agreed problem statement. Testing can include a small pilot study or simply a critical discussion of all the elements that went into the business case. The business case can be a short 1–2-page summary following the structure of the scorecard shown in the Appendix.

While the scorecard should be seen as guidance on how to structure the outcomes of the IL, **the aim should NOT be to optimize the solution for a high overall score**. Instead, all participants should work together to agree on an innovative solution that best represents the view of the IL on how the outlined problem should be approached and solved. The testing and finalising of the solution can all be done in one meeting or workshop or through an iterative approach over one or two additional meetings. Based on the outcomes of the third meeting and in agreement with all participants, the NATURANCE consortium lead can organise additional meetings.

To broaden the applicability of results and outputs, it is essential to validate them through expert review. Additionally, engaging non-experts is crucial for driving innovation and ensuring that outputs are validated against social and political dimensions. Leveraging the KN and its members can further enhance this process by validating and improving the deliverables, ensuring they are robust and widely applicable across various contexts.

Expected outcome: Comprehensively described and tested innovation or solution. A 1–2 page summary describing the outcomes of the IL in the shape of a business case following the scorecard template in the Appendix.

5. Building a Business Case

In broad terms, a business case is a structured analysis designed to justify the adoption of sustainable and equitable innovative green insurance and investment solutions for NbS. It involves analyzing policy and governance conditions that either facilitate or hinder such solutions. It may identify exemplary practices and policy reforms that unlock the business potential of NbS and enable their wider deployment. A business case may include a series of in-depth assessments, policy briefs, and a database of policy cases focused on upscaling NbS. It may also reflect principles for equitable and sustainable financing / insurance business models.

When building a business case for the NATURANCE ILs, the approach taken is at the discretion of the NATURANCE consortium partner leading the IL, in collaboration with the IL participants. The business case should ultimately be tailored for policymakers. While the scorecard gives an overview of what questions need to be addressed in the ILs, the following example from the WBCSD may be another useful reference, or guide, for NATURANCE consortium members when identifying additional key questions to be discussed in the ILs, when building the business case.

5.1 Case Study: WBCSD Blueprint

The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), whose shared vision is a world where over 9 billion people can thrive within the planet's boundaries by 2050, has developed a comprehensive blueprint² for NbS. This blueprint provides guidance on how companies can build business cases for using NbS to address their challenges and opportunities, while also delivering positive impact on climate, nature and equity. The blueprint comprises a six-stage process for companies to follow, as summarized below.

Six-Stage Process

1. Identify key business challenges and opportunities

- Aggregate information on current challenges and opportunities from existing assessments.
- Typical challenges include risk management, regulatory requirements, supply chain resilience, profitability, and ESG commitments.

2. Explore NbS relevant to the company's challenges and opportunities

- Identify NbS that align with the company's specific challenges and opportunities.

² <https://www.wbcsd.org/resources/nature-based-solutions-blueprint/>

- 3. Collect information on overall benefits and trade-offs from the chosen NbS**
 - Gather data on the overall benefits and potential trade-offs of selected NbS, including economic, environmental, and social impacts.
- 4. Develop an initial design for the chosen NbS**
 - Create a preliminary design for the chosen NbS, considering site-specific factors and stakeholder inputs.
- 5. Estimate costs of the proposed NbS**
 - Calculate the costs associated with implementing the NbS, including CAPEX and OPEX.
- 6. Compare NbS options to other solutions across full range of benefits and costs**
 - Use tools like Decision Matrix Analysis to compare NbS with traditional solutions across a range of criteria, weighing benefits and costs to identify the best option.

6. Reporting and disseminating the Innovation Lab outcomes (Post-lab Phase)

On completion of the IL, the outcomes need to be summarized and reported. For that the NATURANCE consortium member leading the IL will use the business case summary and other documentation or minutes created during the IL to summarise and evaluate the suggested solution. Together with the results of the other ILs, the outcomes will be published in a synthesis report. LSE, along with the IL partners will be compiling the business case summaries into the final deliverable report before submitting for final review.

6.1 Quantitative assessment of Innovation Lab outcomes using scorecard summary

If appropriate to the topic of the IL, it is recommended that the NATURANCE consortium member leading the IL scores the outcomes of the IL. For that they may use the questions in the scorecard template shown in the Appendix. The scorecard consists of four sections:

(1) Problem statement, current baseline & innovation, (2) implementation & execution, (3) Financing, (4) Impact.

Each section consists of **three core questions to be answered using the material and documentation from the IL.**

Each question is scored from **1 (lowest) to 5 (highest)**. In case a question cannot be answered or assessed based on the outcomes of the IL, the question is scored 0. This means each of the four sections **can reach a maximum of 15 points, resulting in a maximum total score of 60 for all four sections.** For each score proposed by the NATURANCE consortium lead, they will provide a **short 1-2 sentence rationale** for that score. The scoring and scales should not be revealed to participants ahead of the IL to avoid the discussion throughout the ILs being influenced by attempts to maximize the 'score' of the innovative solution.

The completed scorecards are shared with the participants of the IL, to provide their feedback on whether the outcomes are accurately represented in the scorecard summary. Participants can challenge the suggested scores assessed by the NATURANCE consortium lead in case they think the score does not accurately reflect the outcome of the IL. It is important to note that ILs are **not designed as competitive spaces and the scores are meant to be a guidance for the intended audience and not the outcome of a competition.**

Expected outcomes: Completed scorecard including score rationale for each of the twelve questions.

6.2 Qualitative assessment of Innovation Lab

To further evaluate the effectiveness and likely impact of the IL, a qualitative assessment by independent observers such as LSE or CMCC may be undertaken, facilitated by the NATURANCE consortium member leading the IL.

This evaluation should address several key questions – such as those outlined below – to ensure a comprehensive analysis:

- a. Has a strategic approach been taken from the outset [*clear objectives*]
- b. Has the innovation lab attracted contributions from a diverse stakeholder group [*innovation*]
- c. Does the innovation lab have plans to reach target audience with findings / exploitable output [*impact*]
- d. Will the innovation lab be effective in informing policy [*policy maker engagement*]
- e. Will the innovation lab be effective in reaching decision-makers [*actionable uptake*]
- f. Has the innovation lab created and identified sufficient follow-up opportunities [*impact with implementable solutions*]
- g. Has the innovation lab been sufficiently joined up across WPs [*leverage project structure*]
- h. Has the innovation lab applied learnings from previous rounds of ILs [*feedback loop*]
- i. Has the innovation lab facilitated application of learnings to subsequent deliverables [*leverage ILs*]

6.3 Innovation Lab report structure

This section provides guidance for consortium partners on how to compile and structure the final report for the IL. The final report is crucial for documenting the activities, outcomes, and impacts of the lab. It is essential to provide a comprehensive description of the IL, detailing its specific objectives, the stakeholders involved, and the overarching role of the project in these activities.

Additionally, the report should elaborate on the legacy of the labs, focusing on their long-term impact and sustainability. Clear plans and support for future activities must be articulated, including how they will be seamlessly integrated into the NATURANCE project's broader scope. Furthermore, it is crucial to explain how the KN and ILs will be interconnected to ensure a cohesive and effective approach to achieving the NATURANCE project's goals.

The final report should be around 20+ pages, not including annexes, and should include the following sections:

Overview and executive summary (1-2 pages)

Provide a short snapshot overview of the innovation lab structure, participants³, events, focus area and a reflection on impact. Summarize the key topics, work completed, and results achieved. This section should be concise and provide a snapshot of the IL's outputs and impacts.

Introduction and purpose of the IL (2-3 pages)

Provide background information on the IL, including the rationale (why), the objectives (what), and an overview of the IL's approach (how). Clearly articulate the intended objectives of the IL. Link these objectives to broader societal challenges and the demand for innovative solutions in the specific case explored by the IL.

Details of the IL (8-10 pages)

Provide a detailed description of the IL and how it was conducted, including the following information:

Organizations Involved: List all organizations that participated in the IL. Include the total number of organizations and provide a brief description of each.

Experts Participating: Document the number of experts who participated in the knowledge exchange. Include their fields of expertise and their contributions to the IL.

³ Please ensure the names of any experts/participants not directly involved in the NATURANCE project are anonymised.

Events Organized: State the number of events organized, including workshops, seminars, and other gatherings. Where applicable provide statistics on attendance (average and total).

Outcome/Results (5-7 pages)

Detail the outcome of the IL's discussions and any analytical or evidence-gathering work conducted, decisions made, agreement found. Provide a thorough explanation of what was agreed upon, highlighting any significant findings or conclusions. Explain the business case developed as a result of the IL. Bring in quotes and statements from participants where applicable.

Concluding reflection on the business case (3-4 pages)

Provide a concluding evaluation of the IL and the business case developed. This should be done qualitatively. To ensure comparability across different ILs include a table that summarizes reflections on the following points:

- if and how the results of the IL may be used by participants
- applicability beyond the IL use case – i.e. if and how this could be used elsewhere (sector, region, hazards etc.)
- any barriers, issues that arose from the IL process including 'lessons learned' for others
- impacts, both immediate and long-term

Next steps / future work (1 page)

To ensure wider dissemination of key findings and insights, it is crucial to translate these results into accessible formats for broader audiences. Planned follow-up activities should be clearly defined, including strategies to encourage the uptake and practical use of the results.

Additionally, a well-prepared strategy and detailed plans for the exploitation of these results are essential. Targeting policymakers with specific, policy-related outcomes and recommendations, including guidance on where investments should be prioritized, will further enhance the impact and utility of the project's findings.

Report Annex

Include summaries/ links of meetings and events associated with the IL.

6.4 Innovation Lab review and submission process

This section outlines the process for review and submission of the IL report.

LSE will advise on and co-ordinate the process and timeline for the review and submission of final reports, for each round of ILs.

Review and submission process

- *3 months before deadline*: Submit a draft outline of the final report to LSE for initial feedback.
- *1 month before deadline*: Submit a draft version of the final report to LSE for feedback. Incorporate any feedback and finalize the document.
- *Deadline*: Incorporate any feedback received and submit the final version of the report by the deadline.

Round II

For Round II of the ILs, the deadline for submission of final IL reports to LSE is c.1 month before the end of the review period (i.e. by around end February 2025), to allow sufficient time for internal review and consolidation of the reports into the final Round II deliverable by LSE.

Firm dates will be confirmed by LSE as part of the ongoing engagement with NATURANCE consortium partner leads throughout Round II.

References

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Appendix

A. Scorecard

	Summary	Scale (1 to 5, 0 in case question cannot be assessed)	Score
Problem statement, Current baseline & Innovation	How well does the developed business case (<i>max. 5 points per question</i>): 1. Identify the challenge/need for innovation regarding the link between nature and insurance? 2. Provide a solution to the identified challenge? 3. Offer a new and innovative solution?	1 (Significantly below current baseline) 5 (Significant improvement to current baseline)	x/15
Implementation & Execution	How well does the developed business case (<i>max. 5 points per question</i>): 1. Identify the key groups and stakeholders that are needed for implementation? 2. Outline the implementation strategy? 3. Outline and address risks surrounding the implementation?	1 (Implementation hasn't been fully explored) 5 (Implementation is very likely)	x/15
Finance	How well does the developed business case (<i>max. 5 points per question</i>): 1. Demonstrate the ability to get financed? 2. Describe the need, use and source of funding? 3. Outline sustainable finance expectations?	1 (Financing options not at all explored) 5 (Feasible financing options fully explored)	x/15
Impact	How well does the developed business case (<i>max. 5 points per question</i>): 1. Show how the innovation can lead to a positive impact for nature? 2. Show how the innovation can have a positive impact for the insurance sector? 3. Show that the innovation can lead to a positive impact for society and communities including climate resilience, equity and participation?	1 (No or negative impact) 5 (Highly significant impact)	x/15
Total			x/60

B. Innovation Lab Canvas

